

1 **Federated Learning in Forest Resource Modelling and Monitoring: Bridging Data**
2 **Confidentiality and Collaborative Research**

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22 Highlights

- 23 • Harmonized cross-border forest resource assessment requires integration of field and
24 remote sensing data.
- 25 • Confidentiality constraints of field plot coordinates limit field and remote sensing data
26 alignment for cross-border monitoring.
- 27 • Federated Learning addresses data-sharing barriers through distributed computing.
- 28 • Federated Learning models match or outperform baseline model performance.

29

30 Abstract

31 The European Union's proposed forest monitoring regulation underscores the urgent need for
32 harmonized, cross-border forest resource assessments that integrate both remote sensing and
33 field-based National Forest Inventory (NFI) data. However, confidentiality constraints on NFI plot
34 coordinates present a significant barrier to aligning these datasets, thereby limiting the
35 development of unified forest monitoring systems that can fully leverage the potential of Earth
36 Observation data. To overcome these data-sharing limitations we explored the effectiveness of a
37 privacy-enhancing technique, named Federated Learning (FL), that is a form of distributed
38 computing aimed at preserving the privacy and confidentiality of data owned by different
39 organizations. This methodology has been tested in this paper for the collaborative modelling
40 and mapping of forest timber volume across four European countries: Norway, Sweden, Finland,
41 and Italy.

42 We developed a time-series convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture tailored to
43 integrate 40 years of Landsat or 7 years of Sentinel imagery and terrain variables with
44 harmonized NFI data from 85,199 sample plots. The Federated Learning framework enabled

45 model training to be conducted locally within each country, maintaining data privacy by
46 transmitting only model weights to a central server. The central server then aggregated these
47 model weights into a single global model, which was shared with participants for updating their
48 local models. This federated methodology was compared to traditional country-specific and
49 centralized modelling strategies.
50 The best-performing national FL models achieved predictive performance comparable to the
51 baseline national models, with pixel-level root mean squared errors (RMSE) ranging from 54% to
52 68% across countries. The FL global model that used the same aggregated model in all
53 countries, showed slightly reduced performance compared to the national FL models in some
54 cases, highlighting the importance of local fine-tuning. We also explored model performance for
55 different input time series lengths and found improved accuracies with longer time series.
56 This research is to our knowledge the first application of Federated Learning in forest science
57 and offers a scalable, privacy-preserving solution for integrating remote sensing and field data
58 across national boundaries. The study demonstrates its application rather than seeking optimal
59 prediction. By aligning with the EU's forest monitoring objectives, this approach facilitates the
60 generation of harmonized models and maps of forest features, like timber volume and biomass,
61 that are critical to support evidence-based forest policy and management. The findings
62 underscore the potential of Federated Learning to transform collaborative environmental
63 monitoring, particularly in domains where data confidentiality and interoperability are critical.
64

65 *Keywords: Forest resource mapping; satellite remote sensing; deep learning; distributed*
66 *modelling; national forest inventory; data privacy*

67

68 1. Introduction

69 The European Commission (EC) has proposed a regulation to establish a comprehensive forest
70 monitoring framework aimed at enhancing the resilience of European forests (European
71 Commission, 2023). This initiative seeks to provide open access to detailed, accurate, and
72 timely information on the status and trends of EU forests, building upon existing national
73 systems and monitoring schemes. This proposal underscores the necessity for harmonized
74 estimates of forest resources across member states to ensure accurate monitoring of the state
75 of European forests. Key objectives of the proposed regulation are developing a robust and open
76 repository of forest information to enable actions ensuring forest resilience, and to supply up-to-
77 date information to inform policy decisions, including information on the state of forests, natural
78 disturbances and forest disasters.

79 The proposed law emphasizes the harmonization of data collection across member states and
80 their integration with satellite observations made available for the entire continent by the EU
81 Copernicus program. National governments will be responsible for complementing satellite
82 retrievals with field data collected during National Forest Inventory (NFI) campaigns, with the
83 objective to ensure comparability between countries and increase spatial resolution and
84 timeliness of forest statistics. This approach aims to address existing disparities in data
85 availability, scope and methodologies among NFIs, promoting a more integrated and coherent
86 monitoring system across the EU. By harmonizing NFI data collection and reporting standards,
87 the EU seeks to enhance the effectiveness and timeliness of forest monitoring, thereby
88 supporting sustainable forest management and contributing to broader environmental and
89 climate objectives.

90 The EU forest monitoring law's requirement to integrate remote sensing data (e.g., satellite
91 imagery) with NFI data presents a unique challenge due to the confidentiality of plot coordinates
92 in many NFI systems. Furthermore, demands for freely accessible NFI data are being made (e.g.
93 Nabuurs et al., 2022). However, plot coordinates in NFIs are often kept confidential to protect
94 landowners' privacy, sensitive ecological data, and prevent any unintended impact on the
95 monitored sites due to vandalism, unauthorized exploitation, or experimental manipulation
96 (Schadauer et al., 2024). On the other hand, the fusion of satellite and ground data requires
97 geospatial coordinates to accurately extract remote sensing features corresponding to the same
98 areas where field data is collected. Without access to exact coordinates, aligning the two data
99 sources is not possible, severely limiting the integration of field data with remote sensing data,
100 potentially leading to mismatches in spatial or temporal scales and ultimately to a sub-optimal
101 use of satellite and ground information. In particular, the missing fusion of remotely sensed and
102 ground data complicates the ability to create harmonized spatial datasets that meet the EU's
103 needs for comprehensive forest monitoring. Addressing these challenges and finding workable
104 solution is therefore critical to achieving the EU's goal of a unified and actionable forest
105 monitoring system that relies on both field and remote sensing data.

106 One approach for solving this issue is implementing a centralized analysis platform where all
107 data are collected and where models are calibrated on the combined dataset of satellite and
108 ground information with stringent rules to secure data confidentiality. For this purpose, first
109 remote sensing data must be linked to field data on a national level without revealing exact plot
110 coordinates to third parties. Afterwards, all extracted data is collected in one central place
111 where all further analyses are conducted (Miettinen and Breidenbach et al., 2025a; Miettinen
112 and Breidenbach et al., 2025b). However, this builds on the trust in the security of the central
113 organization and hardware storing the data. In addition, this approach is exposed to the risk that
114 plot-coordinates are unveiled from the reverse-engineering of the extracted remote sensing
115 data.

116 The limitation of centralized analysis could be addressed with a federated approach, based on
117 the concept of distributed computing, where model calibration is performed locally (in this case
118 on country level) and only calibrated model parameters are shared. Federated Learning (FL) is a
119 framework which enables machine learning approaches on a large, distributed dataset, without
120 sharing the data itself (Hurtado Ramírez et al., 2023). While the centralized approach is based on
121 manual model building on the servers of analysts, FL is based on automated model building on
122 the servers of data owners. This approach, while commonly used in fields such as medical and
123 communication research (e.g. Casella et al., 2023; Gupta et al., 2023), to our knowledge has not
124 been applied to forest science until now.

125 A wide range of machine learning approaches have been successfully applied to remote sensing
126 tasks, each offering specific advantages depending on the nature of the data and the
127 classification problem. Among these, convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have emerged as a
128 leading method for processing and interpreting imagery due to their ability to learn spatial
129 hierarchies of features (LeCun et al., 2015; Prince, 2025). CNNs are particularly effective when
130 extended to sequential data and have shown strong integration potential within FL frameworks.
131 Their applicability to satellite image time series has been validated in multiple studies, which
132 highlight their capacity to extract temporal patterns in a data-driven manner (Pelletier et al.,
133 2019; Perbet et al., 2024; Zhong et al., 2019).

134 This article introduces an approach to using FL in combination with NFI data and time series
135 remote sensing data to model forest timber volume with advanced AI methods, while providing a

136 technological safeguard to secure the confidentiality of critical information. The objective of this
 137 paper is not to find the best performing model but to demonstrate the potentials and benefits of
 138 the FL approach in generating large-scale maps by combining sensitive NFI data with remote
 139 sensing retrievals and compare the results to the centralized approach. The study is based on
 140 predictively mapping standing tree volume in four European countries, Norway, Sweden,
 141 Finland, and Italy.

142

143 **2. Materials**

144 In the following we describe the input data in sections 2.1 and 2.2, and data pre-processing in
 145 section 2.3. Modelling will be described in section 3. These steps are graphically depicted in
 146 Figure 1 steps 1-4.

147 *Figure 1: Overview of processing steps. 1. Data consisting of Remote sensing (RS) based data (Landsat, Sentinel 1 and*
 148 *Sentinel 2, terrain data) and NFI data (timber volume). 2. Data pre-processing. 3. Model training and evaluation. 4.*
 149 *Model prediction and mapping. FL = Federated Learning.*

150

151 **2.1. National Forest Inventory (NFI) field data**

152 We used harmonized data from the sample plots of the NFIs of four European countries:
 153 Norway, Sweden, Finland, and Italy (Figure 2).

154

155 *Figure 2: Study area comprising Norway, Sweden, Finland, and Italy.*

156

157 NFI field surveys were conducted according to national procedures and designs vary from
158 country to country.

159 In Norway, the NFI is based on a stratified design with a systematic grid of 3 km x 3 km in the
160 lowland region, 3 km x 9 km in the low-productive, and 9 km x 9 km in the birch-dominated
161 mountain region in Finnmark (Breidenbach et al., 2020). Plot centers are marked invisibly with a
162 metal pole buried in the ground, and the center coordinates were measured using a handheld
163 GPS. In addition, for so far 74% of the sample plots located in forest, the coordinates have been
164 measured using survey-grade GNSS equipment to obtain more precise coordinates. The latter
165 data were used where available. For trees with a diameter at breast height ≥ 5 cm (dbh, 1.3 m
166 above ground), tree properties are measured on circular plots of 250 m² around the plot center.
167 Tree heights are measured for a subsample of approximately 10 trees per plot. We used the
168 permanent sample plots of the Norwegian NFI in this study.

169 In Sweden, the NFI uses a geographically stratified design, and the inventory is carried out using
170 two independent systematic field samples, one with temporary and one with permanent
171 clusters of plots (Fridman et al., 2014). The country is divided into five strata with decreasing
172 sampling intensity towards the north. There are between 4 and 12 plots within square or
173 rectangular cluster and the distance between plots within a cluster varies from 300 m in the
174 south to 600 m in the north. Plot centers are marked invisibly with a metal stick buried in the
175 ground, and the center coordinates are measured using handheld GPS receivers with a
176 horizontal positional accuracy of approximately 5 m. Approximately 10,500 sample plots
177 belonging to 1,400 clusters are field surveyed annually. Of these, 54% are permanent plots that
178 are revisited every five years while the remaining 46% are temporary plots that are measured
179 only once. On both temporary and permanent plots, trees with a diameter less than 4 cm are
180 measured on two 0.5 m radius plots, and trees with a diameter between 4 cm and 10 cm are
181 measured on a 3.5 m radius plot. If the diameter is 10 cm or more, the trees are measured on

182 plots with 7 m or 10 m radius on temporary and permanent plots, respectively. Tree heights are
 183 measured for a subsample of approximately 3 trees per plot.

184 In Finland, the NFI is based on a stratified design using six regions, in which the field plots are in
 185 clusters (Korhonen et al., 2024). We used the data sets of the four largest sampling regions,
 186 excluding those from the Northernmost Lapland and the Åland Islands. The four sampling
 187 regions have each five clusters of field plots in square cells, whose side length varies from 12 km
 188 to 20 km. The clusters have 8 - 11 field plots according to the sampling region and permanent or
 189 temporary type of the cluster. In a cluster, the field plots are after every 250 or 300 m on two lines
 190 at a right angle. The plot center coordinates in forest are measured using survey-grade GNSS
 191 receivers and further corrected using data from the base stations. The tree data of this study
 192 have been measured on concentric circular plots having either radius of 9 m (dbh \geq 9.5 cm) or 4
 193 m (4.5 \leq dbh $<$ 9.5 cm). Heights are measured on average for 3 - 4 trees per plot.

194 In Italy, data from the third National Forest Inventory (INFC2015) were used (Gasparini et al.,
 195 2022). The inventory was conducted using a three-phase sampling design (Fattorini et al., 2006).
 196 In the first phase, the national territory was covered with a systematic grid of 1 km² quadrats.
 197 Within each quadrat, one point was randomly selected using a tessellation stratified sampling
 198 (TSS) scheme (Cordy & Thompson, 1995). In the second phase, more than 30,000 of these points
 199 located within forest and other wooded land were visited in the field to assess qualitative forest
 200 attributes. In the third phase, a random subsample of over 7,000 points was selected for
 201 detailed field measurements. These third-phase plot centers are marked invisibly with a buried
 202 metal pole. Each plot consists of a single circular area with a 13 m radius (531 m²), where all
 203 trees with a diameter at breast height (DBH) \geq 5 cm are measured (D'Amico et al., 2025). Tree
 204 height is recorded for a subsample of approximately 10 trees per plot. Plot centers are
 205 georeferenced using handheld GNSS devices.

206 Plot-level timber volume (growing stock) from these NFIs were harmonized following detailed
 207 definitions and instructions (nFIESTA, 2024), assuring consistent data across all countries.
 208 Timber volume was defined as the above-ground volume of living trees with a minimum dbh of 7
 209 cm, including all parts of the stem from the stump up to a diameter of 7 cm and including all
 210 branches with a minimum diameter of 7 cm. It was not possible for Finland to include the branch
 211 volume. Considering the prevailing tree species groups in Finland, the branch volume was
 212 deemed negligible in this case. A total of 85,199 sample plots measured in the years between
 213 2017-2023 and located inside forest defined according to the international forest definition
 214 (FAO, 2023) were used in this study (Table 1, Table 2).

215 *Table 1: Details of NFI data for each of the four countries: number of primary sampling units (n PSUs), number of*
 216 *sample plots (n plots), minimum, mean, and maximum timber volume, and years of data collection.*

	n PSUs	n plots	Timber volume (m ³ -ha)			Years of data collection
			min	mean	max	
Finland	7,295	40,828	1	129	1,121	2019 – 2023
Italy	6,671	6,671	0	173	1,836	2017 – 2020
Norway	10,271	10,271	0	118	1,158	2019 – 2023
Sweden	5,663	27,429	0	148	2,543	2017 – 2021
Total	29,900	85,199	0	137	2,543	2017 – 2023

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 218
 219

220 *Table 2: Number of NFI sample plots per country and year.*

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Finland	-	-	8,100	8,066	8,184	8,159	8,319
Italy	56	3,953	2,643	19	-	-	-
Norway	-	-	2,053	2,016	2,043	2,062	2,097
Sweden	5,545	5,464	5,540	5,571	5,309	-	-
Total	5,601	9,417	18,336	15,672	15,536	10,221	10,416

221

222 2.2. Remote sensing data

223 Remote sensing data consisted of a time series of 40 years of Landsat images collected
 224 between the years 1984-2023, 7 years of Sentinel 1 and Sentinel 2 images collected between the
 225 years 2017-2023, and additionally terrain variables including elevation, slope and aspect.
 226 Landsat and Sentinel satellite data were processed to generate annual composites suitable for
 227 multi-temporal analysis.

228 For Sentinel-2 (2017–2023), medoid composites were created from a total number of 119,346
 229 images acquired between June and October, applying a 70% cloud cover threshold to limit
 230 location errors caused by excessive cloud contamination (Francini et al., 2023; Kennedy et al.,
 231 2018). Each composite was created at 10 m resolution including surface reflectance from the
 232 red, green, blue, near-infrared (NIR), and short-wave infrared band 2 (SWIR2), and derived
 233 spectral indices such as the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Enhanced
 234 Vegetation Index (EVI), Normalized Burn Ratio (NBR), Moisture Stress Index (MSI), Normalized
 235 Difference Moisture Index (NDMI), and Tasseled Cap Brightness (TCB), Greenness (TCG), and
 236 Wetness (TCW) (Parisi et al., 2023).

237 Sentinel-1 data (2017–2024) were processed separately for ascending and descending orbits.
 238 Annual median composites were computed from a total number of 76,132 ascending and
 239 75,534 descending images (Mullissa et al., 2021), both for the VV and VH polarization bands at
 240 10-meter resolution.

241 For Landsat (1984–2023), annual medoid composites were generated from a total number of
 242 77,061 scenes acquired between May and September, using the same cloud threshold as for
 243 Sentinel-2. Preprocessing included de-spiking and temporal gap-filling via linear interpolation.
 244 From these composites, the bands blue, green, red, NIR, SWIR1, and SWIR2 were used, along
 245 with a suite of indices: NDVI, EVI, NBR, Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI), Normalized
 246 Difference Built-up Index (NDBI), Enhanced Mangrove Vegetation Index (EMVI), and Tasseled
 247 Cap components for brightness (TCB), greenness (TCG), wetness (TCW), and the Tasseled Cap
 248 Angle (TCA) (Huete, 2012; Parisi et al., 2023).

249 For the terrain variables, the Copernicus Global Digital Elevation Model was used to derive
 250 elevation above sea level, aspect, and slope (Copernicus, 2015). Additionally, approximate plot
 251 coordinates (rounded to 1 km x 1 km grid and corresponding to inspire grid cells) were added to
 252 the feature set.

253 All remote sensing data were available wall-to-wall for the four countries (Figure 2) and were
 254 used for the features that served as predictors in the models with $F = \{F_L, F_S2, F_S1S2\}$
 255 features for Landsat and terrain, Sentinel 2 and terrain, and Sentinel 1 and Sentinel 2 and terrain,
 256 respectively, and where the number of features were $F_L = 21$, $F_S2 = 18$, and $F_S1S2 = 22$.

257 2.3. Data pre-processing

258 During data preprocessing (as described in Step 2 of Figure 1), all satellite time series pixels and
259 terrain data intersecting a 100 m² buffer (radius of 5.64 m) around the center of each NFI field
260 plot were extracted. This was done by each country using exact plot coordinates. For each plot
261 and year, weighted means were computed. All observations with at least one pixel value per plot
262 and a minimum of 50% plot coverage were included in the analysis.

263 The data were further pre-processed to ensure that the input was formatted and scaled
264 appropriately for optimal model performance with a convolutional neural network designed to
265 handle time series data. The data were split into three subsets: training and validation data sets
266 for model training, and a test data set unseen by the models and used for independent
267 evaluation of the final models (Prince, 2025). The training and validation sets comprised 70%
268 and 15% of the data, respectively. The independent test set comprised 15% of the data. The data
269 was then sorted chronologically by the year the remote sensing data was acquired to maintain
270 temporal consistency. For each plot, the remote sensing time series data was ended in the same
271 year in which the field data was collected to ensure temporal alignment between the field and
272 the remote sensing data. The target variable and features representing only one point in time
273 (terrain features and approximate geographic coordinates rounded to 1 km x 1 km) were added
274 to the data. Single missing values within the time series were interpolated. To create the full time
275 series of 40 years of Landsat data for field plots that were collected before the year 2023, the
276 missing years at the beginning of the time series (before 1984 for Landsat data, and before 2017
277 for Sentinel data) were filled by applying zero-padding to ensure that all input data had the same
278 shape. The dimension of the data was: $(1, n \text{ features}, t \text{ years})$, where 1 corresponds to one pixel
279 per NFI sample plot (1 weighted mean value in case of more than one intersecting pixel); n
280 features corresponds to all feature variables and include spectral, terrain and spatial data; and t
281 years denotes the number of temporal observations per feature (Figure 3).

282 Furthermore, the Landsat and Sentinel data sets were cut into different time series lengths $T =$
283 $\{T_L, T_S\}$ by cutting years off from the start of the time series to test the effect of time series
284 length on timber volume modelling. For Landsat data, the 40-year time series was cut into
285 shorter lengths such that $T_L = \{40, 30, 20, 7, 4\}$, where T_L indicates the time series lengths in
286 years for the Landsat data set. The 7-year Sentinel time series was cut into one shorter length
287 such that $T_S = \{7, 4\}$. The 4 years correspond to the maximum common time series length using
288 the common newest field data collected in 2020. This was done to avoid zero-padded data at
289 the beginning of the already relatively short time series for countries with older NFI data.

290

291

292 *Figure 3: Data matrix structure for observations of one pixel.*

293

294 Features and target variables were scaled using

295
$$x' = \frac{x - \mu}{\sigma} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

296 where x' is a normalized feature or target variable, x is its unscaled version, μ is the mean and σ
297 the standard deviation of the feature variable in question in the training data. After fitting the
298 scaler on the training data, the scaler was then used to transform all datasets.

299

300 3. Methods

301 In this section we will first describe the modelling approaches baseline (BL) versus Federated
302 Learning (FL), since this is the main focus in this article. Afterwards we will describe the specific
303 model architecture we used here. However, in the FL approach, various model types where
304 model weights or parameters can be aggregated, can be used.

305 3.1. Modelling approaches

306 We trained non-federated BL models for each individual country separately using each country's
307 individual data set, and a large model using the combined data of all countries. These two model
308 types we call BL models. Subsequently, we fitted federated models using the FL framework.

309 **Individual and centralized baseline (BL) models**

310 As a baseline and for comparison with the federated approach we fitted individual country
311 specific models and, in addition, one centralized model using a combined data set of all country
312 data sets (Figure 4 A). The models were trained using the training and validation data sets, and
313 the final models were evaluated using the independent test data sets that were unseen by the
314 model during training. The centralized model was additionally applied to each country's
315 independent test dataset individually. These models were used as baseline, to which we
316 compared the results of the federated models.

317 **Federated Learning (FL) models**

318 In this study, we employed a FL approach described in Hurtado Ramírez et al. (2023) to
319 implement and evaluate our model architecture in a distributed modelling framework. We used
320 the Python library Flower (Beutel et al., 2020). While FL is normally characterized by
321 decentralized data storage and communication across multiple remote client devices or
322 servers, we chose to simulate this setting by hosting all client datasets on a single centralized
323 server while still treating each client data set separately. This approach enabled us to focus on
324 the design and validation of the FL workflow, including client-specific training, aggregation of
325 model weights, and evaluation, without introducing additional complexity from network
326 communication or infrastructure-related variability.

327 To implement the FL models, we employed the four participating countries, each acting as a
328 client. A central server orchestrated the training process by initializing a global model with
329 randomly assigned weights. This initial model was distributed to all clients, who then performed
330 local training using their respective datasets. Upon completion of local training, each client
331 transmitted its updated model weights back to the central server. The server aggregated these
332 weights to update the global model, which was subsequently redistributed to all clients. This
333 iterative process enabled each local model to benefit from the collective knowledge of all
334 clients, without direct data sharing, thereby preserving data privacy (Figure 4 B). The training
335 proceeded through a pre-defined number of rounds of communication between the clients and

336 the server, with the server continuously refining the global model through successive
337 aggregations. During the final communication round each client saved its locally fitted model
338 resulting in a customized fine-tuned local model (Figure 4 B), and the server saved the resulting
339 global aggregated model.

340 To address data heterogeneity across clients, we employed the FedProx algorithm (Li et al.,
341 2020) for model aggregation. FedProx introduces a proximal term to the loss function, which
342 stabilizes training by mitigating the effects of non-IID (non-independent and identically
343 distributed) data across clients.

344
345 *Figure 4: Overview of the two modelling approaches and fitted models. A) Flow of data in the baseline, non-federated*
346 *approach. Here, country specific models are fit individually, and data are collected centrally and a centralized model*
347 *using a combined data set is fit. B) exchange of model weights in the federated approach, where the data remains with*
348 *its owner and only model weights are iteratively exchanged with a centralized server training a global model. Local*
349 *models benefit through the weights of the global model indirectly from the data of the other countries. In both cases*
350 *harmonisation of NFI data is done.*

351
352 **Technical implementation of the FL communication**

353 To implement FL in Flower, the central server needs to be reachable from the internet and listen
354 on two ports (defaulting to 9092 and 9093). Clients contact the server on these two ports but are
355 never contacted by the server. Authentication is ensured using certificates that are exchanged
356 beforehand. More details can be found in Flower (2025).

357
358 **3.2. Model building**

359 Modelling (step 3 in Figure 1) consisted of building a model architecture and configuring the
360 model by tuning the models hyperparameters. All models were trained including terrain
361 variables, and with various satellite time series lengths of T years.

362 **Time Series CNN Architecture**

363 Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have become the predominant approach for processing
364 and analysing two-dimensional imagery (LeCun et al., 2015; Prince, 2025). However, they are
365 also well-suited for time series data, particularly when adapted to capture temporal
366 dependencies (Ismail Fawaz et al., 2019). CNNs' ability to extract local patterns through
367 convolutional operations makes them effective for time series analysis by applying convolutions

368 along the temporal axis. Several studies have demonstrated the utility of temporal CNNs for
 369 satellite image time series. For instance, Pelletier et al. (2019) applied temporal CNNs for
 370 classification tasks, while Perbet et al. (2024) used them for forest disturbance detection. In this
 371 study, we used such a Time Series CNN (tCNN) architecture for timber volume prediction and
 372 tailored it to the dataset described above. The model was implemented in PyTorch (Paszke et al.,
 373 2019) and designed specifically to handle time series data. The architecture comprises multiple
 374 layers that sequentially process the input, as illustrated in Figure 5 and detailed in steps 1 – 7
 375 below. The description assumes the case where $F = F_L$ and $T = T_L = 40$, but the structure
 376 generalises to all datasets and varying time series lengths.

- 377 1) **Input:** The model accepts inputs with a single channel representing one value per
 378 sample plot (computed as the weighted mean of the values of all overlapping pixels). The
 379 input has $F_L=21$ features and $T_L=40$ time points.
- 380 2) **First Convolutional Layer:** This layer applies a convolutional kernel of size $(F, 5)$, with a
 381 stride of 1 and padding set to half the kernel size to preserve the temporal dimension. It
 382 outputs 8 feature maps of an unchanged length of 40, which are passed to the pooling
 383 layer.
- 384 3) **First Pooling Layer:** A max pooling operation with kernel size $(1, 2)$ and stride 2 reduces
 385 the temporal resolution, resulting in 8 feature maps of length 20.
- 386 4) **Second Convolutional Layer:** This layer uses a kernel of size $(1, 5)$ and the same
 387 padding strategy as the first convolutional layer. It produces 16 output channels while
 388 maintaining the temporal dimension.
- 389 5) **Second Pooling Layer / Identity Layer:** For the maximum time series length, global
 390 average pooling is applied using an adaptive average pooling layer of size $(1, 2)$. For
 391 shorter time series, this is replaced with an identity layer that preserves the input shape.
- 392 6) **Dropout Layer:** A dropout layer follows, randomly zeroing a fraction of the input units
 393 during training to mitigate overfitting.
- 394 7) **Output Layer:** A fully connected layer maps the pooled features to a single output value.
 395 A linear transformation is applied to produce the final prediction.

396

397 *Figure 5: Architecture of the time series CNN model for the Landsat and terrain data set with a single input channel*
 398 *with $F_L = 21$ features and $T_L = 40$ time points. The 7 sections of the graph correspond to the steps 1 – 7 in the text.*
 399 *The first section in the graph corresponds to the input layer. Graph created with software by LeNail (2019).*

400

401 Batch normalizations after the first and second convolutional layers for normalizing the
402 activations from the convolutional layers and enhancing training dynamics by stabilizing the
403 mean and variance of layer inputs were tested but did not improve the training.

404

405 **Time Series CNN Configuration**

406 The model based on Landsat data had $F_L = 21$ features, the model based on Sentinel 2 data
407 had $F_{S2} = 18$ features, and the model based on Sentinel 1 and Sentinel 2 data had $F_{S1S2} = 22$
408 features. We trained the tCNN model and tuned the model's hyper parameters kernel time, pool
409 time, dropout layer, and weight decay by minimizing pixel level root mean squared error (RMSE)
410 of the validation data of a combined data set of all countries. We performed the hyperparameter
411 tuning for different models with input data of time series lengths T_L and T_S years for Landsat
412 and for Sentinel data, respectively. The final models utilize the mean squared error (MSE) as the
413 loss function, suitable for regression tasks such as predicting continuous variables from time-
414 series data. Optimization was performed using the Adam optimizer with an initial learning rate of
415 0.01 and a weight decay, which helps in regularizing the model by penalizing large weights. The
416 learning rate was gradually decayed using an exponential learning rate scheduler. We used a
417 maximum number of epochs of 300 and an early stopping mechanism based on validation loss
418 with a tolerance of 20 epochs. Model details and tuned hyperparameters are presented in the
419 Appendix in Table 5 and Table 6.

420

421 3.3. Model evaluation

422 For model employment, training and validation datasets were combined, and performance was
423 evaluated using the independent test dataset. We produced model predictions for the
424 independent test datasets using the following models: i) individual, country specific BL models
425 applied to the corresponding country-specific test data sets (individual BL models in Figure 4 A),
426 ii) the centralized BL model applied to the combined country test data set (Centralized BL model
427 in Figure 4 A), iii) the centralized BL model applied to each country-specific test data set, iv) the
428 local FL models, and v) the global FL models applied to the corresponding country-specific test
429 data sets (Figure 4 B). The coefficient of determination (R^2) and RMSE were calculated, and the
430 relative RMSE was obtained by division by the mean of the observed values and multiplying by
431 100. These results were compared across models to assess their performances.

432 We performed the same steps and analyses for the datasets composed of Landsat data,
433 Sentinel 2, and Sentinel 1 and 2 data.

434

435 3.4. Model predictions and mapping

436 For applying the models and creating prediction maps (step 4 in Figure 1), we used the final local
437 FL models to create wall-to-wall prediction maps of timber volume for the countries. To match
438 the ground resolution of the field surveys we resampled the Landsat data from 30 x 30 m to 10 x
439 10 m pixel resolution before making model predictions. The Sentinel data was kept in its original
440 10 x 10 m resolution.

441

442

443 4. Results

444 We present results for models based on Landsat data in the main text. Due to similar patterns,
 445 graphics for the Sentinel data are presented in the appendix.

446 **Full time series**

447 The results of the model predictions using test data are illustrated in the plots of observed
 448 versus predicted timber volume using the Landsat data for the 40-year time series Figure 6. For
 449 the individual BL models using the full 40-year time series of satellite data, RMSE values ranged
 450 from 70 – 105 m³/ha (61% - 69%, R²: 48 – 59). The centralized BL model applied to the country-
 451 specific data sets performed slightly worse than the individual BL models trained for each
 452 country, with RMSE values ranging from 2% - 7% higher and lower R2 values. The local FL models
 453 performed for each country comparably or better than the individual BL and the global FL
 454 models with RMSE values ranging from 70 -106 m³/ha (54% - 68%). The global FL model
 455 performed comparably to the individual BL and local FL models in Sweden and Finland but
 456 showed reduced accuracy in Norway and Italy. Overall, the results showed that the local FL
 457 models performed as good as or better than the BL models. The accuracy metrics of all models
 458 are presented in Table 3. These results highlight the effectiveness of the FL approach,
 459 particularly the local variant, in producing robust and accurate models for timber volume
 460 prediction, even in the presence of heterogeneous data across multiple countries.

461

462 *Table 3: Accuracy metrics of the time series models using 40 years of Landsat, 7 years of Sentinel 2, and 7 years of*
 463 *Sentinel 1 and 2 data. RMSE values are in m³/ha (relative RMSE in %).*

		Baseline		Federated Learning	
		Individual	Centralized	Local	Global
40 years Landsat and terrain data					
NO	RMSE (%)	82 (69%)	87 (71%)	80 (68%)	88 (69%)
	R2	0.51	0.44	0.53	0.43
SE	RMSE (%)	93 (63%)	95 (67%)	93 (63%)	93 (63%)
	R2	0.48	0.46	0.49	0.49
FI	RMSE (%)	70 (54%)	73 (61%)	70 (54%)	71 (57%)
	R2	0.53	0.49	0.53	0.52
IT	RMSE (%)	105 (63%)	137 (67%)	106 (64%)	132
	R2	0.59	0.29	0.58	0.35
centralized	RMSE (%)	83 (61%)	-	-	-
	R2	0.52	-	-	-
7 years Sentinel 2 + terrain					
NO	RMSE (%)	89 (73%)	105 (88%)	88 (72%)	97 (72%)
	R2	0.50	0.30	0.50	0.40
SE	RMSE (%)	95 (65%)	98 (67%)	94 (65%)	104
	R2	0.46	0.42	0.46	0.35
FI	RMSE (%)	70 (54%)	88 (68%)	69 (53%)	78 (55%)
	R2	0.53	0.25	0.54	0.42
IT	RMSE (%)	124 (72%)	160 (86%)	126 (73%)	164
	R2	0.48	0.13	0.46	0.09
centralized	RMSE (%)	87 (63%)	-	-	-
	R2	0.49	-	-	-

7 years Sentinel 1 and 2, and terrain data					
NO	RMSE (%)	88 (73%)	103 (81%)	90 (73%)	95 (71%)
	R2	0.50	0.32	0.49	0.42
SE	RMSE (%)	94 (64%)	98 (66%)	95 (64%)	104 (73%)
	R2	0.47	0.42	0.46	0.34
FI	RMSE (%)	69 (53%)	89 (63%)	70 (54%)	77 (55%)
	R2	0.54	0.23	0.53	0.43
IT	RMSE (%)	123 (71%)	165 (82%)	126 (73%)	167 (87%)
	R2	0.48	0.08	0.46	0.05
centralized	RMSE (%)	86 (63%)	-	-	-
	R2	0.49	-	-	-

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489 *Figure 6: Observed (y-axis) versus predicted (x-axis) timber volume [m³/ha] of the Time Series CNN models using the*
 490 *Landsat and terrain data, including RMSE (RMSE%) and R² values. Rows represent the results for each individual*
 491 *country and for all country data combined (centralized). Columns: Individual baseline (BL) (40y): model fitted using 40*
 492 *years of country specific remote sensing data; Centralized BL (40y): the centralized model fitted with the combined*
 493 *country data and applied to 40 years of country specific remote sensing data; last two columns: Results of the local*
 494 *and global Federated Learning (FL) models using 40 years of remote sensing data.*

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498 **Effect of time series length**

499 RMSE, RMSE%, and R^2 metrics were used to evaluate prediction accuracy across different time
 500 series lengths. Generally, model performance improved with increasing time series length
 501 (Figure 7 for Landsat and terrain models; for Sentinel see Appendix Figure 12 and Figure 13).
 502 Both the individual BL and local FL models exhibited gains in accuracy with longer time series
 503 and demonstrated consistent performance across all countries. The non-federated individual BL
 504 model trained on the 40-year Landsat time series achieved improved RMSE values, ranging from
 505 70 to 105 m³/ha (54% - 69%). The best overall performance was achieved by the local FL models
 506 using the 40-year time series, with RMSE values ranging from 70 to 106 m³/ha (54%–68%). The
 507 global FL model with the same time series length showed similar performance, with RMSE
 508 values between 71 and 132 m³/ha (57%–69%). Similar patterns were observed for R^2 values. For
 509 the models based on Sentinel data, these trends were similar but not as pronounced due to the
 510 shorter time series.

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513 *Figure 7: Line plots of RMSE% values of independent test data for model results (individual BL, local FL, global FL) for*
 514 *data with time series lengths of 4, 7, 20, 30 and 40 years. Note individual y-axes scales for each country.*

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517 **Bias plots in timber volume bins**

518 Bias was calculated as predicted minus observed values. The overall bias of the local FL models
 519 (40 years Landsat) was 1.79, -1.98, -0.25, and -0.48 for the four counties Norway, Sweden,
 520 Finland, and Italy, respectively. Similar values were obtained for the individual BL models.
 521 Overall bias of the global FL models was generally larger except for Sweden with the 40 years
 522 Landsat based global model. Similar patterns were observed for the models based on the other
 523 data sets (Table 4). Relative bias in bins of timber volume for the four countries for all models
 524 using 40 years of Landsat data is shown in Figure 8). As typical for regression approaches, all
 525 models overestimate low timber volume values and underestimate high timber volume values.
 526 Figures of relative bias in timber volume bins for the models based on Sentinel data are shown in
 527 the Appendix (Figure 14 and Figure 15).

528

529 *Table 4: Overall bias, calculated as predicted minus observed values, for the different models and data sets.*

Overall bias	Baseline Individual	Federated Learning local	Federated Learning global
40 years of Landsat and terrain			
NO	1.83	1.79	10.68
SE	-1.30	-1.98	-1.39
FI	-0.25	-0.25	-5.12
IT	0.34	-0.48	48.39
centralized	-0.50	-	-
7 years of Sentinel 2 and terrain			
NO	0.82	1.85	13.37
SE	0.20	-0.11	-3.46
FI	0.79	0.59	12.42
IT	-0.98	-0.15	-18.06
centralized	0.05	-	-
7 years of Sentinel 1 and 2 and terrain			
NO	0.42	1.94	12.69
SE	0.33	1.24	-3.04
FI	0.60	0.64	9.48
IT	-1.56	-1.04	17.29
centralized	0.16	-	-

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535 *Figure 8: aggregated relative bias (%) over all four countries across different timber volume bins for the different models: individual baseline (BL) models using 40 years of data*
 536 *(individual BL (40y)), local federated learning (FL) models using 40 years of data (local FL (40y)), and global FL models using 40 years of data (global FL (40y)).*

537

538 **Timber volume maps**

539 In Figure 9 we present an overview and two close-ups of our prediction maps together with
540 corresponding satellite images. The first close-up shows Landsat based predictions and RGB in
541 southern Norway around the Norwegian and Swedish border. The second close-up shows
542 Sentinel based predictions and RGB in north-central Italy.

543

544

545 *Figure 9 Overview and two close-ups of the prediction maps with corresponding satellite images. The upper close-up*
546 *represents Landsat based local FL model predictions with corresponding satellite image. The lower close-up*
547 *represents Sentinel based local FL model predictions with corresponding satellite image.*

548

549 **5. Discussion**

550 This study demonstrates the potential of Federated Learning (FL) as a viable and privacy-
551 preserving approach for forest resource modelling and monitoring with the combination of plot
552 and remotely sensed data, which has not been explored in previous studies in this field. Our
553 findings show that local FL models can achieve predictive performance comparable to
554 centralized models across the participating countries. This is an important result, as it highlights
555 FL's capacity to address data confidentiality concerns related to field plot coordinates, while
556 maintaining model accuracy across countries.

557 **Comparison with previous work**

558 Our results are consistent with those of Miettinen et al. (2025), who produced Pan-European
559 forest maps using a combination of satellite-based earth observation data and national forest

560 inventory plots using the centralized approach, where all data were collected and stored in one
561 data base. Using the local FL model, we achieved RMSEs for Norway, Sweden, and Finland of 70
562 – 93 m³/ha (54% - 68%), with a combined value of 80 m³/ha (60%) for these three countries,
563 while Miettinen et al. (2025) reported RMSEs for timber volume of 76 m³/ha (53%) in the boreal
564 region (Norway, Sweden, and Finland combined. Using the local FL model in Italy, we achieved
565 an RMSE of 106 m³/ha (64%), while Miettinen et al. (2025) in a southern region (southern
566 Germany, Switzerland, Austria, south-east France, and entire Italy, Area 11 in that study)
567 reported an RMSE of 178 m³/ha (62%).
568 Koma et al. (Under preparation) found comparable results for modelling timber volume in
569 Norway and Finland using Sentinel 1, Sentinel 2, and PALSAR-2 data and a UNet-based deep
570 learning model. Using only Sentinel 2 data, they found RMSE ranging from 61% to 73%, bias
571 ranging from -7.9% to 2.1%, and R² ranging from 0.41 to 0.58. Combining Sentinel 1, Sentinel 2
572 and PALSAR data, they reported RMSE ranging from 57% to 72%, bias ranging from -2.5% to
573 2.7%, and R² ranging from 0.42 to 0.63. These results are in line with our findings.

574 **Client Contributions and Model Dynamics in Federated Learning**

575 The influence of individual clients on the global FL model is a critical aspect of system
576 behaviour. Our study highlights several mechanisms that govern this dynamic. i) Sample-Based
577 Weighting: In FL, client updates are weighted by the number of local training samples, which
578 naturally reduces the influence of clients with limited data; ii) Local Fine-Tuning: The ability of
579 clients to fine-tune the global model locally is essential. It allows each client to adapt the shared
580 model to its specific data distribution, ensuring that useful local patterns are still captured even
581 if the global model is slightly biased; iii) Fairness and Collaborative Gains: While FL may not yield
582 uniform performance improvements for all clients, it fosters fairness by enabling clients with
583 small or noisy datasets to benefit from the collective knowledge of the group. In the present
584 study we observed poor performance of the global FL model in Norway and Italy. Corresponding
585 to the discussion above, this is related to smaller sample sizes in Norway and Italy (6,671 and
586 10,271, respectively) compared to Sweden and Finland (40,828 and 27,429, respectively). Due
587 to the weighted aggregation function in FL, the larger clients dominate over the smaller clients.
588 However, this effect does not hold for the local FL models, where accuracies comparable to or
589 better than the individual baseline models were consistently observed.

590 While we used a Time Series CNN model in the present study, the FL approach can be used with
591 other model types as well, where model weights or parameters can be aggregated in a
592 meaningful way.

593 **Implications for European Forest Monitoring**

594 The European Commission proposed a European Forest Monitoring Regulation, emphasizing the
595 need for timely, spatially detailed and harmonized forest information across EU member states.
596 A critical aspect in achieving this advancement in the EU forest monitoring is the protection of
597 National Forest Inventory (NFI) plot locations that leads to the impossibility to fully integrate
598 remote sensing and ground data. These plots are often situated on private land and are revisited
599 over long time periods. Public disclosure of their locations could lead to vandalism,
600 unintentional disturbance, bias in harvesting regimes, or (under)exploitation of sensitive
601 ecological or economic resources, which could violate landowner privacy and lead to
602 undermining trust in national inventory programs (Schadauer et al., 2024). Maintaining the
603 confidentiality of plot locations is therefore essential for ensuring the scientific integrity,
604 security, and continuity of long-term forest monitoring. Our findings suggest that FL can play a

605 pivotal role in overcoming these criticalities and achieving the objectives of a European Forest
606 Monitoring system that leverage on the same fusion level between remote sensing and plot data
607 as in the centralized modelling approach, while guaranteeing confidentiality of NFI plot
608 locations. Furthermore, by enabling secure and collaborative modelling across national
609 datasets, FL supports the integration of remote sensing and field data for generating harmonized
610 forest resource maps across large spatial domains. These outputs are essential for supporting
611 the formulation and implementation of evidence-based policy related to the forest sector, the
612 development of forest adaptation plans, the sustainable management, and international
613 reporting related to climate mitigation and biodiversity conservation.

614 **Time series lengths and bias**

615 Both the individual and local FL models benefitted from longer time series. This was most
616 obvious for the 40 years Landsat data, where most improvements were observed until a time
617 series length of 30 years. However, this was not the case for the global FL models in Norway and
618 Italy, where RMSE and R^2 did not improve with longer time series. This is also reflected in the
619 large overall bias of the global FL models in Norway and Italy.

620 When looking at the bias in bins of timber volume, all models overpredicted in low timber
621 volume ranges, and underpredicted in high volume ranges, which is a common phenomenon in
622 all empirical regression models (Mehtätalo & Lappi, 2020, page 101).

623

624 6. Conclusion

625 This study establishes Federated Learning (FL) as a scalable, privacy-preserving solution for
626 forest resource modelling and monitoring. Local FL models demonstrated predictive
627 performance comparable to individual baseline (BL) models, while effectively managing
628 heterogeneous data across countries. The results benefitted from longer time series of remote
629 sensing data, which was most obvious for the 40 years Landsat data set, where we compared
630 five different time series lengths. For the 7 years Sentinel data set this effect was not that
631 pronounced due to shorter time series lengths. Our aim was not to find the best performing
632 model for timber volume prediction, but to demonstrate the applicability of FL for combining field
633 and remote sensing data while preserving sensitive data.

634 A European Forest Monitoring System will require harmonized, cross-border forest assessments
635 while upholding data sovereignty and privacy. FL directly supports these goals by enabling
636 collaborative model training across national datasets without requiring the exchange of raw data
637 or sensitive geospatial information. This makes FL particularly well-suited for integrating remote
638 sensing and field data across EU member states, facilitating the generation of harmonized
639 timber volume and biomass maps. In doing so, FL not only aligns with the EU's Forest Monitoring
640 objectives but also strengthens the foundation for evidence-based forest policy, sustainable
641 management, and international scientific collaboration.

642

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651

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770 7. Appendix

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772 *Table 5: Model architecture of the Time Series CNN (tCNN) model and global parameters of the federated training.*

Model architecture	
Conv-1	
Input-channel	1
Output-channel	8
stride	1
Conv-2	
Input-channel	8
Output-channel	16
stride	1
Training parameters	
Optimizer	Adam
Initial learning rate	0.01
LR decay scheduler	Exponential LR
Gamma	0.95
Loss function	Mean Squared Error
Batch size	32
Max number of epochs	200

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775 *Table 6: Tuned hyperparameters found by minimizing RMSE of the validation data, for the models using Landsat,*
776 *Sentinel 2, and Sentinel 1 and 2 data, respectively.*

Data set	Landsat + terrain			Sentinel 2 + terrain			Sentinel 1+2 + terrain		
N time points	40	30	20	7	4	7	4	7	4
Model Hyperparameters									
Kernel time	5	4	4	2	2	4	3	5	5
Pool time	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	1	1
Dropout conv	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2
Adaptive pool time	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Weight decay	3.32e-4	3.11e-4	1.77e-4	2.68e-4	2.84e-4	3.27e-4	1.85e-4	1.68e-4	2.08e-4

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788 *Figure 10: Observed (y-axis) versus predicted (x-axis) timber volume [m³/ha] of the models using the Sentinel 2 and*
 789 *terrain data, including RMSE (RMSE%) and R² values. Rows represent the results for each individual country and for all*
 790 *country data combined (centralized). Columns: Individual baseline (BL) (7y): model fitted using 7 years of country*
 791 *specific remote sensing data; Centralized BL (7y): the centralized model fitted with the combined country data and*
 792 *applied to 7 years of country specific remote sensing data; last two columns: Results of the local and global*
 793 *Federated Learning (FL) models using 7 years of remote sensing data.*

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799 *Figure 11: Observed (y-axis) versus predicted (x-axis) timber volume [m³/ha] of the models using the Sentinel 1+2*
 800 *terrain data, including RMSE (RMSE%) and R² values. Rows represent the results for each individual country and for all*
 801 *county data combined (centralized). Columns: Individual baseline (BL) (7y): model fitted using 7 years of country*
 802 *specific remote sensing data; Centralized BL (7y): the centralized model fitted with the combined country data and*
 803 *applied to 7 years of country specific remote sensing data; last two columns: Results of the local and global Federated*
 804 *Learning (FL) models using 7 years of remote sensing data.*

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RMSE % Across Time Series Lengths

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810 *Figure 12: Line plots of relative RMSE values of independent test data for Sentinel 2 and terrain data based models*
 811 *(individual BL, local FL, global FL) for data with time series lengths of 4 and 7 years. Note individual y-axes scales for*
 812 *each country.*

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RMSE % Across Time Series Lengths

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826 *Figure 13: Line plots of relative RMSE values of independent test data for Sentinel 1+2 and terrain data based models*
 827 *(individual BL, local FL, global FL) for data with time series lengths of 4 and 7 years. Note individual y-axes scales for*
 828 *each country.*

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836 *Figure 14: aggregated relative bias over all four countries across different timber volume bins for the different models using Sentinel 2 + terrain data: individual baseline (BL) models*
 837 *using 7 years of data (individual BL (7y)), local federated learning (FL) models using 7 years of data (local FL (7y)), and global FL models using 7 years of data (global FL (7y)).*

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843 *Figure 15: aggregated relative bias over all four countries across different timber volume bins for the different models using Sentinel 1+2 + terrain data: individual baseline (BL) models*
 844 *using 7 years of data (individual BL (7y)), local federated learning (FL) models using 7 years of data (local FL (7y)), and global FL models using 7 years of data (global FL (7y)).*

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